

Review Article

A Review of Monkeypox (Mpox) Disease: Clinical Manifestations, Diagnosis, Treatments and Preventions

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Abstract

Monkeypox is a zoonotic disease caused by the monkeypox virus, an Orthopox virus. According to World Health Organization (WHO) statistics, monkeypox has been identified as an epidemic in 127 nations so far, and it is spreading quickly over the globe. WHO has declared mpox a public health emergency of international concern (PHEIC) twice, the first time in May 2022 and the second time in August 2024. The clinical infestation of mpox may typically begin with a prodromal phase that includes fever, headache, muscle aches, backache, and swollen lymph nodes. This is followed by the onset of a distinctive rash that usually appears one to three days after the fever. The rash progresses through several stages, starting as macules, then becoming papules, vesicles, and finally pustules before crusting over. Lesions can occur on various parts of the body, including the face, palms, soles, and mucous membranes. Patients may also experience other symptoms such as fatigue, chills, and respiratory symptoms, although these can vary in severity. Even though it is clinically unclear from other pox-like infections, laboratory diagnosis is essential. There is no specific treatment for human monkeypox virus infection, however, smallpox vaccination can defend counter to the disease. This review was focused on clinical manifestation, epidemiological situation, diagnosis, treatments and prevention measures of Monkeypox disease in an existing knowledge to raise awareness from health professionals, public population, national level to the globe as whole to adopt effective preventions measures to reduce the risk of disease to be pandemic after COVID-19. Monkeypox is now a public health concern disease as the WHO declared for the second time a public health emergency of international concern (PHEIC). The new cases of the disease are reported in non-endemic countries which make the other countries implement emergency prevention strategies to avoid the spread of the disease. Humans can exhibit signs and symptoms that are disturbingly like chickenpox, Smallpox, or other vesiculopustular rashes. An outbreak requires precise and prompt laboratory identification. Infection may be prevented by avoiding contact with infected animals and reducing respiratory exposure of infected person. Also, by avoid handling clothes, sheets, blankets or other materials that have been in contact with an infected animal or person. The ongoing surveillance of country level could promote prevention strategies in globe.

Keywords: Mpox (Monkeypox), Public health concern, Zoonosis, Epidemiology, Diagnosis, Treatment, Prevention, Africa.

Introduction

Monkeypox is an infectious disease that can cause a painful rash, enlarged lymph nodes, fever, headache, muscle ache, back pain and low energy. Most people fully recover, but some get very sick [1]. The monkeypox (mpox) virus – is a zoonotic virus that belongs to the species Monkeypox virus, Poxviridae family of the genus Orthopox virus [2]. Other viruses that infect humans and belong to this genus include cowpox virus, variola, with the latter being the cause of the eradicated smallpox disease [3]. The natural host of HMPV is unknown; nevertheless, it has a wide range of mammalian reservoirs, including rats (the main group), squirrels, dormice, and monkeys [3].

According to World Health Organization (WHO) statistics, monkeypox has been identified as an epidemic in 127 nations so far, and it is spreading quickly over the globe [4]. WHO has declared mpox a public health emergency of international concern (PHEIC) twice, the first time in May 2022 and the second time in August 2024 [1].

Monkeypox virus was first identified in 1970 in Democratic Republic of the Congo during the global campaign to eradicate smallpox, a disease caused by Variola virus, another orthopoxvirus [5]. In the West and Central Africa region, Monkeypox still occurs infrequently despite the World Health Organization's (WHO's) 1980 declaration that Smallpox had been eradicated [6]. A pet store that imported mice from Ghana in 2003 caused an epidemic in the United States [7]; [8]. From October 2017 to February 2018, the recent Mpox pandemic in Nigeria was catastrophic to the healthcare system [9]. In the current Monkeypox incident, a UK resident who arrived in Nigeria on April 20, 2022, visited Lagos and Delta State before departing Lagos on May 3, 2022, and landing in the UK on May 4, 2022, was involved [10]. Several experts, including specialists, were unable to identify what caused the epidemic early on. In September 2017, the following Mpox occurrence in Nigeria, the country regularly reported isolated viral cases from across all states, as per Nigeria Center for Disease Control (NCDC) [11]. 22 states reported 558 cases and eight deaths between September 2017 and April 30, 2022. There are 46 suspects,

and fifteen confirmed cases from seven states had been registered with no recorded death (Nigeria Centre for Disease Control (NCDC), [11]. For its virulence, which is just next to the Variola virus, the source of Smallpox, with a 10% rate of death, Monkeypox virus is a potential biological warfare weapon [12] like SARS-CoV-2 [13]; [14]; [15]; [16]; [17].

Consequently, both healthcare professionals and the public need to be educated about the clinical manifestations, diagnosis, treatments, prevention, and control of the disease. This review will explore the current knowledge of Monkeypox, emphasizing its clinical features, epidemiology, transmission, and preventive strategies. Additionally, the rise in monkeypox cases in non-endemic regions, particularly after the WHO declared mpox a public health emergency of international concern (PHEIC) for the second time in August 2024 [1], this spread presents a public health risk to other countries like Somalia. This situation calls for disease surveillance at the national level, with prompt identification and reporting of suspected cases being crucial for effective preventive actions.

Etiological Agent of Monkeypox and its characteristics

The monkeypox virus is a double-stranded DNA virus that belongs to the same group as variola, cowpox, and vaccinia viruses classified within the genus Orthopoxvirus, family Poxviridae. One unique trait of Monkeypox virus among other poxviruses is the broad range of host species tropism—from rope squirrels to sooty mangabey [18]—which may have allowed prolonged zoonotic circulation of Mpox virus in the wild.

Morphologically, Mpox virus exhibits an ovoid or rectangular brick-shape characteristic of poxviruses, measuring 200 × 250 nm, decorated with membrane surface tubules or filaments and a biconcave core component as seen on electron micrograph (**Figure 1**) [19].

Figure 1. Negative-stained transmission electron micrograph of M-type MPXV particle (A). Thin section of viral particles on skin sample, showing ovoid mature virions on the left and spherical immature virions on the right. Micrographs are courtesy of the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) Public Health Image Library (PHIL) [20] (B). Schematic representation of MPXV virion structure (C).

Based on the sequence identity of all strains isolated from the African continent, MPXV can be differentiated into two clades: strains isolated from West Africa and from the Congo Basin (or Central Africa), where inter-clade sequence homology is at most ~95% while intra-clade homology approaches 99% [Likos, A.M, et al., 2005]. Besides geographic distribution, these two clades vary in clinical presentation, severity, and transmission [21]. The West African clade appeared milder, without reported mortalities until the 2017–2018 Nigeria outbreak, whereas the case–fatality ratio for the Congo Basin clade was reported to be approximately 10% [22]. The preliminary phylogenetic investigation revealed that the current 2022 outbreak is mainly related to the West Africa clade [23].

There are two genetically distinct clades for Monkeypox virus: clade I, with sub-clades Ia and Ib [24], and clade II, with subclades IIa and IIb [25]. Sub-clade Ia is often referred to simply as clade I [26].

Monkeypox virus clade I has been reported in the past as associated with severe clinical symptoms and higher mortality compared to clade II [27] until the 2022 global outbreak, which was instead driven by Monkeypox virus clade IIb [28]. Clade IIb is characterized by less severe illness and lower mortality.

Epidemiology of Mpox diseases

Epidemiological scenario in African Countries

Since humans were first infected with the virus through direct contact with diseased animals thousands of years ago, Mpox has likely been present in Sub-Saharan Africa for thousands of years [29]. There is currently no information about Mpox viruses' reservoir. Though, there is evidence that monkeys, like humans, are accidental hosts. The reservoir will likely be one or more mice or monkeys found in central Africa's forest [30].

A total of 47 human cases of Mpox have been reported in Sub-Saharan Africa from 1970 to 1979, with 38 of these occurring in the DRC and the remaining taking place in Cameroon, the Central African Republic, Gabon, Cote d'Ivoire, Liberia, Nigeria and Sierra Leone [30]; [31]. The DRC cases all occurred near tropical rainforests and appeared connected to animal interaction. Seven of the 47 diseases documented were lethal. The secondary spread was shown to be the leading prospective source of contagion in four cases, with the second occurrence proportions of 7.5% between nearby family members living in the same house and 3.3% between all exposed interactions. Many cases have been recorded in the DRC since 1980 [29].

Annual mpox case and death counts during 2018–2021 were compiled from national surveillance data, WHO bulletins and published case reports or outbreak investigations and were verified with country surveillance teams. Cases occurred in 6 African countries: Cameroon, Central African Republic (CAR), DRC, Nigeria, Congo and Sierra Leone. Since 2018, DRC has reported >3000 suspected cases per year, with a peak of 6216 suspected cases and 222 deaths in 2020. During 2018–2021, 79 confirmed mpox cases in CAR in 7 localities represented a notable increase over previous years; an average of 9 mpox outbreaks have occurred annually since 2018. In addition, during this period, 9 cases were confirmed in Cameroon, where no human case of mpox had been documented since 1989; in a case that occurred in 2018, the virus shared genetic similarity with a clade II strain previously isolated in Nigeria, [32] and additional cases were

reported in various regions of the country in 2020 and 2021. Two cases each were reported in Congo and Sierra Leone during 2018–2021.

Since 1 January 2022, cases of mpox have been reported to WHO from 19 Member States across Africa. As of 25 August 2024, a total of 6 062 laboratory confirmed cases, including 55 deaths, have been reported to WHO. [1].

In 2024, as of 25 August 2024, 14 countries have reported 3 659 confirmed cases, including 32 deaths. The three countries with the majority of the cases in 2024 are Democratic Republic of Congo, (n = 3 244), Burundi, (n = 231), and Central African Republic, (n = 45). [1].

According to the latest Africa CDC figures, as many as 17, 541 mpox cases and 517 deaths have so far been reported from 13 African countries. The Democratic Republic of the Congo, the epicenter of the current outbreak, accounts for 96% of all cases and 97% of all deaths reported in 2024. [33].

Kenya reported a second confirmed case of the disease in the country. The patient, an adult male truck driver, was identified at the Malaba One Stop Border Post in Busia County, showing symptoms after traveling from the outbreak epicenter in DRC. [34].

As new cases emerging in neighboring countries, Somalia is at risk for an mpox outbreak. Although no confirmed cases have been reported in the country yet, it is essential to enhance public health awareness and maintain ongoing surveillance at border posts and airports to implement effective preventive measures.

Outbreak in the in the EU/EEA

On 15 August 2024, Sweden reported one imported case of mpox due to Mpox virus clade Ib [Public Health Agency of Sweden [35]. The case is an adult who returned from an African country where mpox virus clade Ib transmission has been reported. Previously, and as of 8 August 2024, 22 662 confirmed Mpox cases have been reported by 29 countries in the EU/EEA via The European Surveillance System (TESSy) as part of the outbreak driven by clade Iib. Most cases (93%) were reported during an intense period of

circulation in 2022. In 2023, 860 cases were reported in 21 EU/EEA countries while so far in 2024, 685 cases have been reported by 20 EU/EEA countries. This indicates continued circulation of Monkeypox virus in the EU/EEA, but at very low levels. Information on the virus clade was reported for very few (2.1%) of all mpox cases reported to TESSy since 2022. All cases reported to TESSy as of 8 August 2024 were from clade II.

Figure 2: Countries where monkeypox virus clade I and/or clade II have been detected [36].

1.0 Data by country

Summary of Mpox cases

As of 25 Aug 2024

Country	Total cases	Total deaths	Case fatality ratio (%)	Cases in 2024 ¹	Deaths in 2024 ¹	Cases in the past two weeks ²	Deaths in the past two weeks ²	Clades detected in country	Date of last report
Democratic Republic of the Congo	4,489	27	1%	3,244	25	9	0	Clades Ia and Ib	18 August 2024
Burundi	231	0	0%	231	0	148	0	Clade Ib	25 August 2024
Central African Republic	92	2	2%	45	1	0	0	Clade Ia	18 August 2024
Nigeria	902	9	1%	41	0	2	0	Clade II (a+b)	25 August 2024
Côte d'Ivoire	28	1	4%	28	1	18	1	Clade II (a+b)	18 August 2024
South Africa	29	3	10%	24	3	0	0	Clade II (a+b)	18 August 2024
Congo	49	2	4%	23	0	2	0	Clade Ia	25 August 2024
Liberia	23	0	0%	6	0	0	0	Clade II (a+b)	18 August 2024
Cameroon	50	5	10%	5	2	0	0	Clades Ia and II (a+b)	18 August 2024
Rwanda	4	0	0%	4	0	0	0	Clade Ib	18 August 2024
Uganda	4	0	0%	4	0	2	0	Clade Ib	25 August 2024

Summary of Mpox cases

As of 25 Aug 2024

Country	Total cases	Total deaths	Case fatality ratio (%)	Cases in 2024 ¹	Deaths in 2024 ¹	Cases in the past two weeks ²	Deaths in the past two weeks ²	Clades detected in country	Date of last report
Kenya	2	0	0%	2	0	1	0	Clade Ib	25 August 2024
Gabon	1	0	0%	1	0	1	0	Clade Ia	25 August 2024
Morocco	5	0	0%	1	0	0	0	Clade II (a+b)	17 March 2024
Benin	3	0	0%	0	0	0	0	Clade II (a+b)	18 August 2024
Egypt	3	0	0%	0	0	0	0	Clade II (a+b)	18 December 2022
Ghana	127	4	3%	0	0	0	0	Clade II (a+b)	18 August 2024
Mozambique	1	1	100%	0	0	0	0	Clade II (a+b)	18 August 2024
Sudan	19	1	5%	0	0	0	0	Clade Ia	9 April 2023
Total	6,062	55	1%	3,659	32	183	1	–	–

¹ From 01 Jan 2024 to 25 Aug 2024

² From 12 Aug 2024 to 25 Aug 2024

Source of the Table: 2022-24 Mpox (Monkeypox) Outbreak: Global Trends World Health Organization, Produced on 28 August 2024. https://worldhealthorg.shinyapps.io/mpx_global/ [1].

Transmission of mpox diseases

Animal to Human Transmission: Animal-to-human transmission of mpox occurs from infected animals to humans from bites or scratches, or during activities such as hunting, skinning, trapping, cooking, playing with carcasses or eating animals. The animal reservoir of the monkeypox virus remains unknown and further studies are underway. [1]. Interacting diseased monkeys, rats, rabbits, Gambian giant squirrels, Porcupines, dormice, prairie dogs, and gazelles has been identified as a possible transmission mode [37].

Ingestion of insufficiently prepared meat from infected animals, inoculation from infected animals' mucocutaneous sores, particularly once the skin barrier is ruptured due to bites, scratching, or other disturbances, or inoculation from mucocutaneous lesions on diseased faunae are methods for the virus to reach people (**Figure 3**) ([38]; [37]).

Human to Human Transmission: Mpox spreads from person to person mainly through close contact with someone who has mpox, including members of a household. Close contact includes skin-to-skin (such as touching) and mouth-to-mouth or mouth-to-skin contact (such as kissing), and it can also include being face-to-face with someone who has mpox (such as talking or breathing close to one another, which can generate infectious respiratory particles). [1].

People can also contract mpox from contaminated objects such as clothing or linen, through needle injuries in health care, or in community settings such as tattoo parlours. [1].

During pregnancy or birth, the virus may be passed to the baby. Contracting mpox during pregnancy can be dangerous for the fetus or newborn infant and can lead to loss of the pregnancy, stillbirth, death of the newborn, or complications for the parent. [1].

FIGURE 3

The primary host and transmission route of MPXV, eating infected animals as a food source, is the major cause of animal-to-human virus transmission. Healthy people can contract the virus by intimately contacting someone who is infected.

Figure 3: The primary host and transmission route of Mpox Disease [39].

Pathogenesis of mpox virus

MPX infection begins with a cutaneous or respiratory epithelial infection in affected animals or people. A primary viremia results in systemic infection, followed by secondary viremia, which causes epithelia infection and ulceration in the skin and mucosa. Through oropharyngeal secretions, viruses replicate on mucosal surfaces and spread to close contacts. Even though MPXV is capable of evading host immune responses, the density of viral particles in oropharyngeal secretions, proximity and duration of contact, and viral survival affect virus transmission [38].

Clinical Manifestations of mpox

Mpox causes signs and symptoms which usually begin within a week but can start 1–21 days after exposure. Symptoms typically last 2–4 weeks but may last longer in someone with a weakened immune system. [1].

Common symptoms of mpox are rash, fever, sore throat, headache, muscle aches, back pain, low energy and swollen lymph nodes.

Figure 4: The signs and symptoms of Mpox Disease [39].

The mpox rash often begins on the face and spreads over the body, extending to the palms of the hands and soles of the feet. It can also start on other parts of the body where contact was made, such as the genitals. It starts as a flat sore, which

develops into a blister filled with liquid that may be itchy or painful. As the rash heals, the lesions dry up, crust over and fall off. [1].

Diagnosis of Mpox Disease

The diagnosis of monkeypox virus involves a combination of clinical assessment and laboratory testing. Clinically, healthcare providers look for characteristic symptoms, including fever, lymphadenopathy, and a distinctive rash that progresses from macules to vesicles and pustules. To confirm the diagnosis, laboratory tests such as polymerase chain reaction (PCR) are utilized, which can detect the viral DNA in lesion samples, blood, or other bodily fluids. Serological tests may also be performed to identify specific antibodies against the monkeypox virus. Given the similarities in clinical presentation with other poxviruses, accurate laboratory confirmation is crucial for effective management and control of the disease [46]; [43]; [41]

Treatment of Mpox disease

There is no specific treatment of mpox. The treatment, like with most viral diseases, is symptom control. There are, though, preventative measures that can assist avoid an epidemic.

The septic person must be isolated, keep covered lesions and wounds, and wear a mask even more than probable till all lesion crusts break off and a new skin layer form. In extreme circumstances, for exploratory usage, medicines with efficacy against orthopoxviruses in animal trials and severe vaccinia vaccination sequelae may be evaluated. There is an approved treatment for smallpox known as brincidofovir, tecovirimat, and vaccinia immunoglobulin, as well as an inhibitor of intracellular viral release known as tecovirimat and which has shown efficacy against Mpox in animals [40]; [41]; [42].

Prevention and Control of mpox disease

The prevention and control of mpox (Monkeypox) disease are critical for mitigating its spread and impact. As outbreaks continue to occur, particularly in non-endemic regions, effective strategies are essential. Increasing awareness among healthcare professionals and the public about mpox's signs, symptoms, and transmission routes is vital. Health authorities should disseminate information on safe practices for travelers to affected areas [43].

Robust surveillance systems must be implemented to detect and monitor mpox cases promptly. Suspected cases should be reported to health authorities for timely investigation and response [41].

Thorough contact tracing for confirmed cases is essential to identify and monitor individuals who may have been exposed. Quarantine measures should be enforced for close contacts to prevent further transmission [44].

Personal protective equipment (PPE) should be used by healthcare providers when caring for infected individuals. Isolating suspected and confirmed cases until they are no longer contagious is critical for infection control.

Avoiding contact with wild animals, particularly rodents and primates, in endemic areas is important. Monitoring the health of animals in these regions can help reduce the risk of zoonotic transmission [45].

Promoting proper hand hygiene, including regular handwashing and using hand sanitizer, is

essential, especially after contact with potentially infected individuals or materials. Public education on avoiding contaminated items is necessary.

Issuing travel advisories for areas with mpox outbreaks, along with guidance on vaccination and safety measures, is crucial for protecting travelers. Advising against contact with sick animals and individuals in affected regions is necessary.

Engaging local communities and civil society organizations can help raise awareness and ensure that prevention strategies are culturally appropriate and effective. Involving high-risk populations in these efforts can reduce stigma and encourage reporting.

Ongoing research is needed to better understand mpox, including its transmission dynamics and effective treatments. Continuous monitoring of the epidemiology of mpox is essential to adapt prevention and control strategies accordingly.

Vaccination

Vaccination with the vaccinia virus can provide protection against mpox. Expanding vaccination efforts, especially for high-risk groups such as healthcare workers and those in contact with infected individuals, is crucial [46].

Concerns of a new pandemic

The declaration of WHO for the second time in a public health emergency of international concern (PHEIC) for mpox disease in August 2024, has increased the fear of the disease becoming pandemic after COVID-19. Many at-risk countries have deployed surveillance teams at border posts and airports to mitigate the spread of mpox. In Somalia, although no cases have been reported, the Ministry of Health has announced plans to enhance prevention efforts and raise public awareness about the disease.

The concerns surrounding a new pandemic of mpox disease necessitate immediate action from global health authorities, governments, and healthcare systems. A robust public health response is essential to mitigate the risk of a pandemic. This includes enhancing surveillance

systems, improving laboratory testing capabilities, and ensuring timely reporting of cases. Public health authorities must also engage in effective risk communication to educate communities about preventive measures.

Conclusions

Monkeypox has become a significant public health concern, as the WHO has declared a public health emergency of international concern (PHEIC) for the second time. New cases are emerging in non-endemic countries, prompting nations to implement emergency prevention strategies to curb the disease's spread. Symptoms in humans can closely resemble those of chickenpox, smallpox, or other vesiculopustular rashes. Swift and accurate laboratory identification is crucial during an outbreak. To prevent infection, individuals should avoid contact with infected animals and limit respiratory exposure to infected persons. It is also important to refrain from handling clothing, sheets, blankets, or other materials that have been in contact with infected individuals or animals. Strengthening infection control measures, such as regular screening and isolating newly infected animals, would greatly aid in controlling epidemics. Good hygiene practices are vital to prevent the virus from spreading through fomites and causing new infections. Vaccination with the vaccinia virus may also serve as a protective measure for animals. To prevent the spread of the disease, an infected individual should limit contact with animals, particularly squirrels and primates.

Recommendations

Take the following actions to prevent infection of the monkeypox disease should implement:

1. Increase awareness among healthcare professionals about travel-related mpox cases, including varied clinical presentations and transmission routes.
2. Ensure timely reporting of surveillance, lab testing, epidemiological investigations, and contact tracing to WHO Surveillance in emergencies.

3. Advise travelers to affected areas on national vaccination guidelines for mpox before departure.
4. Rapidly isolate suspected cases until confirmed negative; if positive, isolate them until symptoms resolve.
5. Implement contact tracing and testing for close contacts of confirmed cases, following Africa CDC protocols.
6. Provide travel advice for individuals visiting or returning from countries with mpox outbreaks.
7. Avoid contact with potentially infected animals, particularly sick or dead ones in endemic areas.
8. Steer clear of items that have interacted with infected animals or humans.
9. Use personal protective equipment (PPE) when caring for infected individuals, including gowns, masks, gloves, and eye protection.
10. Maintain risk communication efforts and collaborate with civil society organizations to reach high-risk population groups.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

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